

NH₄⁺-N, and 10 ppm available NO₃⁻-N. Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was transplanted during 1985 and 1986 wet seasons (May-Oct).

Urea supergranule (USG), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and Musoorie phospho-coated urea (MPCU) as basal incorporated and prilled urea (PU) applied as local split (1/2 at transplanting, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 at 5-6 d before panicle initiation [DBPI]) and standard split (2/3 at transplanting and 1/3 at 5-6 DBPI) were applied at 29, 58, and 87 kg N/ha. MPCU and SCU were broadcast and incorporated at transplanting, USG was hand placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills.

Soil samples were collected randomly from fertilized plots, except in USG plots where they were collected 6-8 cm away from the placement site.

NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N were extracted from the wet soil immediately with 1N sodium sulfate. NH₄⁺-N concentration was determined by modified Nessler reagent method and that of NO₃⁻-N by chromotropic acid method.

NH₄⁺-N content increased with increasing N rates to 30 DT, then decreased (Fig. 1). The decrease may be attributed to uptake by plants, gaseous loss of NH₃, and nitrification-denitrification. The decrease was less with USG.

NO₃⁻-N concentration was very low. At 15 DT, it was higher with PU and MPCU than with USG and SCU (Fig. 2). Plots with USG showed lower NO₃⁻-N, presumably because the USG was placed in a reduced zone where nitrification might be limited for lack of oxygen. With SCU, low concentration of NO₃⁻-N could be due to delayed release of urea and conversion of fertilizer N to NO₃⁻.

2. NO₃⁻-N content in soil as influenced by N rates (a) and sources (b).

The presence of nitrate suggests that nitrification-denitrification losses may be occurring.

These results suggest that formation of soil nitrate can be reduced slightly through the use of modified urea materials. ■

Contribution of flood siltation to boro rice yield and response to N and K

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Floodwater deposits silt and other suspended materials as it starts to recede. The effects of this silting on soil productivity have not been established experimentally.

We evaluated the effects of siltation by floodwater on boro rice in terms of the crop's response to N and K fertilizer Jan-Apr 1988. Land within the Hathazari Farming Systems Research area was

ponded by floodwater about 1.5 m deep for about 15 d.

After the flood receded, three types of soil sampling were done: deposited surface silts, 2.5 cm; original soil, 2.5-15

Table 1. Characteristics of soil sample of flash-flooded ricefields Hathazari, Bangladesh Jan 1988.

Soil sample	pH	Organic matter (%)	K (meq/100 ml)	NH ₄ -N (lg/ml)	Zn (lg/ml)	S (lg/ml)
0-2.5 cm surface silt	6.6	2.35	1.0	22.5	3.0	8
2.5-15 cm soil	5.9	2.45	0.3	17.5	2.5	4
0-15 cm silt and soil	6.0	2.50	0.3	19.5	3.0	7

cm; and whole sample, 0-15 cm. Soil analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Eight fertilizer levels were tested (Table 2) in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

All the P and K, and 1/3 the N were applied basally after final land preparation. The remaining N was topdressed, 1/3 at 25 d after transplanting (DT) and 1/3 at 45 DT. Purbachi rice seedlings (35 d old) were transplanted at 25- × 15-cm spacing. Application of 120 kg N, 34 kg K/ha gave the highest yield. No significant yield differences were found when K was applied at 17-51 kg/ha with 80-120 kg N/ha (Table 2). The relatively low effect of K on grain yield may be attributed to the increased K content of the surface silts. ■

Table 2. Yield parameters of boro rice planted on flash-flooded fields and fertilized with N and K, Hathazari, Bangladesh, Jan-Apr 1988.

Treatment (kg NPK/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain Yield (t/ha)
0-0-0	186.30	45.21	21.15	1.4
0-28-34	213.97	51.09	22.55	2.1
40-28-34	244.89	63.12	23.03	3.0
80-28-0	266.62	72.12	23.09	3.7
80-28-17	276.07	77.67	23.32	4.1
80-28-34	277.42	77.84	23.44	4.1
80-28-51	274.72	77.14	23.60	4.2
120-28-34	308.47	76.67	24.76	4.4
CV (%)	12.44	11.44	2.05	7.3
LSD (0.01)	63.74	15.49	0.50	0.5

^aFrom urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Response of rice to *Azospirillum brasilense* and organic manures on organic- and chemical-fertilized farms in India

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Field trials were conducted in lowland rice culture during Sep 1988-Feb 1989 on two farms in Pondicherry, India, using White Ponni rice variety. One farm (Gloria Land) had adopted organic farming 10 yr before. The other farm (farmer's field) had for several years used only chemical fertilizers.

The field trials were laid out in a randomized block design with nine treatments and four replications. The control plots on the two farms differed; the farmer's field plot received 100:50:50 kg NPK/ha. Other treatments included farmyard manure (12.5 t/ha), leaves of *Azadirachta indica* (6.25 t/ha), and cow dung slurry (5.0 t/ha) alone and in combination with *A. brasilense* (seed, seedling, and soil application).

Grain yield in Gloria Land increased with some treatments (see table). The

Response of White Ponni rice grown in organically and chemically fertilized fields. ^a Pondicherry, India Sep 1988-Feb 1989.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Gloria Land	Farmer's field	Gloria Land	Farmer's field
No addition	5.7	-	8.1	-
100 N-50 P-50 N	-	5.1	-	7.4
Farmyard manure (FYM)	5.9 (3.15)	4.4	8.8 (7.5)	6.9
Green leaf manure (GLM)	6.7 (17.7)	4.1	9.9 (21.9)	6.5
Cow dung slurry (CS)	6.1 (6.1)	4.0	8.7 (7.1)	6.4
<i>Azospirillum</i>	5.9 (2.6)	4.1	7.5	6.5
FYM + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.2 (9.1)	5.1 (1.2)	8.8 (8.2)	7.0
GLM + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.8 (18.2)	4.9	9.8 (19.8)	6.9
CS + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.2 (8.6)	4.9	9.8 (20.5)	6.4
FYM + GLM + CS + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.8 (19.2)	5.7 (13.3)	10.4 (28.3)	7.6 (3.7)
LSD	0.4	0.2	1.7	0.5

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase.

effect on yield of different organic manures with or without *Azospirillum brasilense* varied, depending upon the N content of the organic manures. In the farmer's field, N fertilizer yielded less than the control plot of Gloria Land. Combined application of organic manures plus *A. brasilense* gave significantly

higher grain yield than N fertilizer alone.

In Gloria Land, where organic manures had been applied for several years, *Azospirillum* application did not have a significant effect. In the farmer's field, *Azospirillum* application increased grain yield significantly. Straw yields followed a similar trend. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.